

INTRODUCTION

Currently, digital technologies provide significant assistance in several areas of agricultural development at once: precision farming, process automation and the use of big data increase productivity; in monitoring climatic conditions, optimizing resource use and adapting to new situations; in reducing negative environmental impacts, maximizing the use of water and land resources; allowing for improved quality control from production to sale. Financing in the field contributes to developing new technologies and improving the agricultural sector's competitiveness.

Transition to digitalization of business processes, including financial government support in the AIC, is directly related to implementation of the target program "Creation of a unified information support system for the agro-industrial complex of Russia (2008-2010)", which included several target indicators. Digital technologies are the most critical factor in rural development, and became widespread during the COVID-19 pandemic. Digitalization of agricultural business processes is the most crucial direction for developing agricultural enterprises and increasing competitiveness and socio-economic efficiency. Digital technologies allow optimizing all stages of the production cycle and consumption of various resources, and improving the quality of agricultural products.

The study aims to substantiate the directions of financing and government regulation of implementing digitalization in the AIC.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials were articles in agronomy, economics, finance, and technology published in peer-reviewed journals, including Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing, Precision Agriculture, Agriculture and Human Values, Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering, Artificial Intelligence Review, and International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology.

The statistics on introduction of digital technologies in the agricultural sector were used, in particular, data on the costs of introducing and using digital technologies in the Russian Federation, the main targets of the departmental project "Digital Agriculture", and the leading agricultural producing countries.

Research methods: statistical analysis, comparative analysis, and document analysis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The growth and spread of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic led to imbalances in all sectors around the world, severely disrupting the global economy, the agricultural and food sectors among the most vulnerable ones.

A. Sridhar et al. examine the impact of COVID-19 on the agri-food system and its economy, highlighting critical factors such as food production, demand, rising prices, and supply chain security and sustainability. The authors discuss use of digital tools, mainly AI, machine learning, deep learning, and blockchain technology, in the agri-food sector [1].

As digitalization is increasing in the agricultural sector, so is the number of studies on introducing and using digital technologies in crop and livestock.

M. L. Chizzotti et al. write that the fundamental concept of precision farming is managing spatial variability in production. Similarly, precision animal husbandry aims to manage the variability of each animal or group of animals using software, sensors, actuators, and robotics, as well as collecting, storing, and processing data that provides information for decision-making [2].

J. Monteiro et al. believe digital twins reveal the potential to ensure more rational resource use, food protection, failure prevention, and food traceability [3].

A. Gabriel and M. Gandorfer focus on consistent implementation of precision farming and other digital technologies, as well as use of several technologies in a small agricultural region in southern Germany. According to the authors, Bavarian farmers cannot be described as extremely “digitalized” but show potential adoption rates of 15-20% over the next five years for technologies such as cowshed robotics, application management, and satellite data maps [4].

M. Nehrey & L. Zomchak believe that access to broadband Internet, the availability of gadgets for organizing business processes, and the digital skills of agricultural workers are essential prerequisites for digitalization. According to the authors, modern challenges require innovative thinking from the agricultural sector, introducing new technologies and creating new professions [5]. I. Unay-Gailhard & M. A. Brennen emphasize that technological advances in digital agricultural practices, such as geographical flexibility or the innovative potential of agriculture, increase awareness of new professional opportunities [6].

D. Honc and J. Merta write that smart agriculture can increase yields and efficiency, improve the welfare of farm animals, cultivate high-quality crops, and conserve natural resources [7].

T. A. Shaikh et al. show the potential of ICTs in traditional agriculture and the problems connected to using these. The authors describe the issues of robotics, Internet of Things

devices, and machine learning, as well as the roles of machine learning, AI, and sensors used in agriculture. In addition, drones are being considered for monitoring crops and managing yield optimization [8].

D. K. Kwaghtyo and C. I. Eke write that the emergence of intelligent farming and precision farming based on machine learning opens up opportunities for automated solutions. The authors consider innovations of intelligent agriculture for forecasting key agricultural methods such as soil, yield, and fertilizers, including weather and irrigation models [9].

I. Härtel believes that saturation of the agricultural sector with information and communication technologies leads to a new combination of farming experience, agricultural entrepreneurship, and digital technological competence [10].

D. S. Gangwar et al. explore the economic and environmental performance of traditional and ecological farming practices through a feasibility study of digital agricultural technologies in the Upper Gangetic Plains of northern India. The assessment conducted by the authors contributed to the overall management of agroecological resources by promoting highly optimized, intelligent, individualized, and proactive approaches to farm management [11].

Over the past two decades, digital technologies became increasingly relevant and manifested themselves in various disciplines of plant pathology and integrated pest control. This field is very dynamic, and innovations in sensors, robotics, AI and data interpretation open up new possibilities for detecting plant diseases in an automated and non-invasive manner.

A. K. Mahlein et al. write that the development of machine learning, computer vision, and deep learning methods has significantly influenced methods for detecting plant diseases [12].

D. Agarwal et al. study the problems of using robots in digital agriculture and their advantages over traditional methods [13].

J. Chang writes that digital finance is an essential part of China's financial system and that it changed China's green finance model. According to the author, reduction of agricultural carbon emissions through digital finance can be achieved through the impact of digital finance on farmers' entrepreneurship and innovation in farming technology [14].

S. Ma et al. pay attention to how the development of digital agriculture contributes to reducing carbon emissions in agriculture. According to the authors, agricultural technological progress, the structure of the farm sector, and the education level in rural areas contribute to reducing carbon emissions from agriculture in the region. Strengthening the exchange of digital agriculture between areas and using the intermediate effect of digital inclusive finance can effectively enhance the effect of reducing carbon emissions [15].

Z. A. Telegina et al. consider the prospects of increasing the investment attractiveness of the regional AIC with introduction of digital technologies in terms of capabilities of the federal center and the specifics of Russian regions. Using the example of the Ural Federal District, the

authors present principles and methods that influence the activation and increase of the inflow of investment resources into agriculture [16].

J. Forney et al. believe that state support for the agricultural sector of the economy a condition for successful modernization of agricultural production and for provision of high-quality food products to the population. The authors believe the state should support the creation and development of digital ecosystems in agriculture. Digital ecosystems allow creating more convenient conditions for potential consumers to find the necessary goods and services, which in turn allows improving the quality of customer service and reduce the costs associated with purchasing goods [17].

Thus, no transparent methodologies and standardized criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of investments in digital technologies within the agricultural sector exist. Importantly, not all agricultural enterprises have equal access to financial resources needed for digital transformation. Investigating the factors that influence access to funding (such as credit conditions, government support, and investment programs) is a significant scientific challenge. Additionally, it is essential to examine how financing digital technologies impacts both economic and environmental outcomes, including sustainable development, resource efficiency, and product quality. This requires a comprehensive analysis of current state policies and regulatory frameworks related to agricultural financing and implementation of digital technologies.

RESULTS

In 2018, the Ministry of Agriculture of the Russian Federation developed the departmental project “Digital Agriculture”, which aims to introduce digital technologies and platform solutions to ensure a technological breakthrough in agriculture and achieve productivity growth of agricultural organizations using digital technologies by 2 times by 2024. According to the project, digitalization of agriculture is planned at three primary levels: national, regional, and organizational. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to comprehensively implement digital agricultural solutions and change the approach to training agricultural specialists by forming a large set of digital competencies. With the introduction of specialized programs and sensors, agrarian producers can monitor production stages in real time and evaluate factors affecting their effectiveness, for instance, the humidity level, temperature, lighting, and others. Another critical area of digitalization in agriculture is product sales, logistics, transportation, and inventory management, such as optimization of logistics processes for delivering and storing finished agricultural products, fertilizers, pesticides, seeds, etc.

Despite the difficulties, the Russian agricultural complex demonstrates steady growth in domestic production during the economy's turbulence. Still, to increase productivity at agrarian enterprises further, it is necessary to increase automation using digital solutions. Due to the lack of financial resources, implementing special software tools in business processes remains difficult in the industry, and mainly for this reason, the industry is among the outsiders regarding digital services.

The next most important direction is to improve the accounting and financial management system, which allows automating the accounting of income and expenses, conducting a detailed analysis of economic indicators, and predicting financial results.

Despite the wide range of opportunities for digitalizing business processes, agricultural producers lack qualified specialists with a certain level of digital competencies, financial resources, and sufficient government support. Agricultural producers need to evaluate the effectiveness of digital technologies, subject to the influence of additional factors (seasonality, territorial extent, use of living organisms, duration of the production cycle, etc.), relative to industrial production.

The cost of implementing and using digital technologies increases annually in Russia (see Figure 1).

Дальневосточный федеральный округ	Far Eastern Federal District
Сибирский федеральный округ	Siberian Federal District
Уральский федеральный округ	Ural Federal District
Приволжский федеральный округ	Volga Federal District
Северо-Кавказский федеральный округ	North Caucasus Federal District
Южный федеральный округ	Southern Federal District
Северо-Западный федеральный округ	North-Western Federal District
Центральный федеральный округ	The Central Federal District

Figure 1 Costs of implementing and using digital technologies in the Russian Federation, 2019-2021

If in 2019 the Volga, North Caucasus, and Central Federal Districts showed the largest costs for the introduction of digital technologies, then in 2021, the Northwestern and Far Eastern Federal Districts saw an increase in the costs for the introduction and use of digital technologies.

In 2023, import substitution issues remain a priority [18]. Despite the high rates of development of the agro-industrial complex, saturation of the domestic market with domestic products: grain, sugar, vegetable oil, fish, meat, issues related to the production of domestic seeds, breeding of poultry and animals, production of agricultural machinery and veterinary drugs remain unresolved in the country, which directly affects the food supply to the population. To solve these problems, the government increased state support for the AIC, which will exceed 445 billion RUR in 2023. Financing of the departmental digitalization project of the AIC is also provided. In 2019-2024, it was planned to allocate 118 billion RUR for implementing the Digital Agriculture platform, of which 22.78 billion RUR was allocated for the Aggroresolution module. Financing is also provided to train digital specialists – 5.37 billion RUR; to train high-quality specialists in AI, Russian universities developed appropriate programs for future farmers to study machine learning, intelligent image processing and recognition methods, software development for mobile devices, etc. One form of government support is financial assistance to agricultural producers who implement digital technologies in various business processes, such as subsidies for purchasing farm machinery, equipment, and software. The government is also allocating funds for infrastructure support, such as broadband Internet in rural areas. Another critical area of government support is the financing of scientific projects and innovative initiatives to increase the attractiveness of rural areas. Government support measures contribute to strengthening healthy competition among domestic agricultural producers. Automated control systems are necessary to improve production efficiency in agriculture. Along with digitalization and robotization of agriculture, operational data collection and monitoring of farming enterprises, as well as integration with government systems, especially regarding financial resources, is essential. Agriculture especially needs innovative systems such as accounting and analytical systems that help analyze production and predict market changes, and RPA software robots that can take over desk and office routines.

In Russia as a whole, due to redistribution of budget funds at the end of September 2022, the Ministry of Finance of the Russian Federation decided to reduce expenditures on some national projects, among 14 national projects in 2023, the budget for the national Digital Economy project is expected to be reduced by 30% to 57 billion RUR.

A variety of internal and external factors may significantly affect the degree of implementation of digitalization and automation tools and programs in agricultural business processes [19]. Internal factors include: level of technical equipment, financial condition of

an agricultural organization, reproduction and effective deployment of human resources, investment attractiveness, corporate culture, and an agricultural producer's brand. External factors include availability of digital technologies for domestic production, price level of the introduced technologies, migration processes in rural areas, competition level, development, and infrastructure accessibility.

Agricultural producers must constantly adapt to the changing conditions of a turbulent external environment to offset the negative impact of not only price but also financial and budgetary factors. Let us consider the primary targets of the departmental project "Digital Agriculture" (see Figure 2).

Рост производительности труда	Labor productivity growth
Коэффициент снижения затрат	Cost reduction ratio
Доля инвестиций в цифровые технологии	Share of investments in digital technologies
Доля смарт-контрактов с получателями субсидий	Share of smart contracts with subsidy recipients

Figure 2 Primary targets of the "Digital Agriculture" departmental project

Automation processes are increasingly penetrating the agricultural sector every year. To date, business processes for cultivating land, harvesting, feeding animals, etc., are partially robotized. Sverdlovsk Oblast began to introduce robotic farms in 2015. The flagship companies introducing robotics are the Ural collective farm and the Kilachevskoye agricultural production cooperative of the Irbit municipality. Thanks to the smart farm, milk yields are higher than in renowned agricultural companies in Canada and Germany. Thus, in the market of milk and dairy products, competition is consistently high, which in turn helps meet the needs of all stakeholders in terms of the price-quality ratio. Despite the development of the small and medium-sized business market, the principal turnover in agricultural products belongs to large agricultural producers.

In our opinion, the most critical area of work in digitalization is to improve the state regulation system. The agricultural sector significantly contributes to the country's food security (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 Leading agricultural producing countries

Thus, the Russian Federation occupies one of the leading places in the world in agricultural products and in using agrarian land [20]. Despite Russia's top positions in agricultural production, only about 5% of farming producers use the latest robotics. For instance, 17.8% of agricultural producers use cloud services, 11.6% use the Internet of Things, 2.2% use AI technologies. The situation is slightly better with agriculture's digitalization and business process automation systems. Thus, more than 40% of agricultural organizations use no more than 7% of electronic document management systems and training programs.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Thus, digital technologies can contribute to a more sustainable use of resources [21], reduce environmental impacts, and increase food security [22].

Introducing technologies such as precision farming, IoT (Internet of Things), big data, and AI is becoming necessary, which creates demand for financing. Various countries are developing and implementing programs, including subsidies, grants, and tax incentives, to support digitalization of agriculture.

Using digital technologies, including through state financial support for agricultural producers, will significantly reduce the amount of reporting in the AIC, increase efficiency of industry management, and attract new professions and IT specialists to agricultural production.

Digitalization of business in the Russian AIC is progressing relatively slowly. In our opinion, this is due to insufficient financing, i.e., agricultural producers either only have funds to implement some aspects of digital equipment or no fund at all. In our opinion, primary use of domestic software is essential, especially by state authorities, local governments and organizations, including agricultural ones; a domestic maximally competitive infrastructure for transmission, processing and storage of digital data, an end-to-end information support system for agriculture, and sufficient financial support for digitalization of agriculture are required. The measures of state financial support depend on the most objective data provided by agricultural producers.

State financial support, including for digitalization can significantly increase the number of agricultural producers and help achieve lower prices, which contributes to proper distribution of finances. Therefore, the primary purpose of subsidizing is to ensure financial stability for the farm sector.

Thus, agricultural producers who employ digitalization tools significantly increase their potential for profitability and competitiveness through efficient use of financial resources.

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Received: Jun 10, 2023 | **Accepted:** Sep 14, 2023 | **Published:** Dec 1, 2023

Editor: Arif G. Ibragimov, Russian State Agrarian University – Moscow Timiryazev Agricultural Academy, RUSSIA

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Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.